

GEORGE FRIDERIC HANDEL'S ARIAS: AN ATTEMPT ON A PERFORMER'S INTERPRETATION**Yang Teng***Graduate student,**departments of History and Theory of Performing Arts and Musical Pedagogy of Saratov State Conservatory named after L.V. Sobinov.*

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Abstract

The aim of this research is an attempt to construct a vocal performer's interpretation by working at baroque arias. G. Handel's arias «Pena tiranna» and «Sorge infausta una procella» taken as example, we show that a vocalist should construct an interpretation basing on the affect of the aria. The article explores the content of Handel's vocal pieces, analyses musical means in the arias, outlines the difficulties they contain for a performer, and considers the interpretations done by the leading singers of our days. The choice of dynamic, tempo, articulatory means must be dictated by the effect of the vocal number, by the principles of the baroque music. The article states that a performer's interpretation of Handel's arias must follow artistic and technical realization of the musical texts by the baroque authors.

Keywords: baroque, aria, G. Handel, performer's interpretation, affect.

As defined by M.S. Bogomol'nyi, "the vocal performing mastery" is a "sum of attributes and characteristics defining the level of student's training which act as a creative substance that causes the quality of exercising student's professional knowledge, skills, and competence in his performing practice" [1, p. 277]. We can single out such components of performing mastery as a performer's culture, mastery of vocal technique and basic musical dramaturgy, acting, stage speech and movement. A vocalist must interpret a musical piece on his own, to transform himself into a needed image on the stage and adapt to his stage fright.

The forming of performing mastery for a modern-day vocalist includes an obligatory work on baroque arias. They are based on the bel canto vocal style and therefore are an important part of the technology of sound production and voice that any singer must master. Performing baroque arias demands a well-tuned vocal apparatus, diversity of breathing together with all different kinds of sound attack, voice mobility and fluency, its timbre richness. Through the example of old music arias, many vocal technics including ornamentation are acquired. However, the questions of performer's interpretation of baroque arias are still not studied enough, which makes this research actual and relevant.

An interpretation of a musical work suggests, on the one hand, following style and historical features of an epoch, on the other hand, creating an individual artistic image. Performing of the baroque arias complies with the set of rules that were set by the aesthetics of that period. A singer must be informed of the problems of artistic and technical implementation of the musical texts by the baroque composers. A baroque aria corresponds with a single effect, and its expression demands some adequate artistic means [2, p. 27]. A performer

must consider the rules of ornamentation usage, the dynamic nuances, the agogics, the choice of a tempo, and the articulation. The form of a baroque aria must be constructed carefully too. The creative freedom of baroque singers lay in the free use of ornamentation, rhythmical variations, improvised cadences, agogic freedom. The analysis of early musical arias made by contemporary vocalists shows that it is still inherent for the performing tradition to add ornamentation to the vocal party, especially in the cadences, to include minute melodic or rhythmical changes, to follow the principle of a specific affect, to use the agogic freedom. Such are the interpretations by Max Emanuel Cencic, Jakub Józef Orliński, Philippe Jaroussky, Cecilia Bartoli, Lorenzo Regazzo, Erik Kurmangaliev and other singers who specialize in baroque repertoire and bel canto style of the G. Rossini epoch. As E.V. Kruglova remarks, including "improvisation in the cadences and variation of the musical texts by repetition" are attributes of the creation of a performer's version of a baroque aria.

One of the pinnacles of the baroque musical art are the works by G. Handel. The composer's vocal style has its own characteristic features. If in the works of the Italian composers the bel canto style is linked to the construction of long melodic phrases, the Handel's arias have a more fragmented syntax, which differs from the Italian tradition. The vocal parts of Handel's arias give a detailed reflection of their lyrics, the composer often builds his work upon a genre.

The modern vocalists often approach the aria "Penna tiranna" of Dardano from "Amadigi di Gaula" by G. Handel. The opera seria "Amadigi di Gaula" was written by Handel in 1775 and has three acts. It is based on the libretto by G. Rossi that follows love intrigues. The knight Amadigi and his friend Dardano fall in love with the same woman Oriana. Dardano gets to know this in the first act of the opera when Amadigi shows

him a portrait of his love and Dardano recognizes Oriana. In this dramatic situation, the Dardano's aria "Pena tiranna" reflects the sufferings of his unrequited love to Oriana who loves Amadigi. Let us look at the fragments of the aria's lyrics: "My heart is torn / by all the sufferings of the unrequited love. / Oriana loves Amadigi, / but is cold to me. / Melissa promised to alleviate my sufferings, / but God, it is too late – / my pain cannot be cured by any spell."

The vocal number "Pena tiranna" is an example of an aria lamento that matches the affect of sorrow. Affects in the baroque epoch were understood as "strictly specializes conditions possessing a person from the outside", and composers had to describe them with the most possible accuracy through the musical rhetorical figures [4, p. 60]. The effect of sorrow in Handel's aria is matched with d-moll tonality, the tempo *andante maestoso*, and the sarabande features. The author's remark *maestoso* indicates a character specific to a sarabande: in the baroque period, sarabande was seen as a mourning dance, its specific feature was a solemn gait, so the *maestoso* remark indicates precisely this character. The sarabande genre shows itself in the "Pena tiranna" aria a bit veiled. G. Handel uses $\frac{3}{4}$ time, rhythmical figures characteristic for the dance such as the long dotted and double dotted rhythm. One bar consists of two fourth notes, an eighth rest and an eighth note. The accord texture makes the even gait more significant. In the introduction, we hear the golden sequence that is related to the sarabande genre in Handel's other works too.

The quintessence of sorrow is an intonation of a minor second. It is present already in the orchestra introduction, alternating with an octave leap. Such a combination of intervals reflects not only sorrow and suffering, but the despair of a character who has lost all hope.

The melody of the vocal part also starts with an intonation of a second that sounds in ascension from the V tone of d-moll. After showing the second intonation, the wide leaps for a fifth, a seventh follow without filling and create tension. Gradually a vocalization, a conjunct movement interweaves with the melody. An ascending movement for a third with the use of eighth and sixteenth notes presents the expressive vocalization in the melody. This reflects the specifics of the baroque melopoeia. The texture of the accompaniment is different. G. Handel refuses the accord texture and introduces in the orchestra part a figured level of eighth notes, which gives the music a necessary mobility.

An orchestra intermedia based on the introduction separates the first and middle parts of the three-part form of the "Pena tiranna" aria. Each part begins with an establishing of the d-moll. The middle part begins with a developing thematic invention followed by a thematic reprise. If in the first part the composer digresses into the subdominant tonality (g-moll), the developing thematic invention in the second moves through tonalities actively. There are modulations into c—moll, F-dur, a-moll here. A melodic repetition involves a major key of the same name, D-dur.

By performing the Handel's aria "Pena tiranna" a singer has to use expressive possibilities of the sarabande genre which is a mourning procession dance most fitted to the affect of sorrow and suffering. Usually in arias lamento the vocal part expresses all the emotions. But because of its relation to the sarabande genre in "Pena tiranna" the composer introduces several intertwining melodic lines. Beside the vocal part, one can hear a melodic high voice in the orchestra part, a bass line, and chords as a harmonic support that represent the *ostinato* rhythm of a sarabande.

On each level, the effect of sorrow and suffering is represented differently. Nevertheless, the vocal part must dominate the orchestra texture. Performers of the Dardano part can use dynamic and agogic nuances in their discretion. An interpretation by an Austrian contra tenor Max Emanuel Cencic presents an even voice leading. The singer rarely uses dynamic gradations and introduces them by little. He is very attentive to the pauses that are an important part of the expressive means for a lament aria and symbolize sighs. Max Emanuel Cencic rarely constructs wide phrases; his performance is built more over accentuating of short melodic configurations.

The Polish contra tenor Jakub Józef Orliński also builds his interpretation aiming for an even voice leading. He performs in a reserved manner. The expressivity of the vocal part reveals itself gradually, by adding ornaments and other features. Max Emanuel Cencic and Jakub Józef Orliński follow the principle of terraced dynamics specific to the baroque music.

The performance of the French contra tenor Philippe Jaroussky is more openly emotional. The expressivity of the melodic line is built by introducing dynamic contrasts, short crescendos and diminuendos. Thus, during the four bars we can hear *piano* (two bars) and *mezzo-forte* (two bars). Jaroussky highlights the intonation of a second with a small crescendo with an accent on the upper tone. Such small dynamics intensifications and falls serve to make the melody expressive and the vocal party intense. However, this technique is not typical for baroque music since it breaks the principle of the terraced dynamics. On the other hand, Philippe Jaroussky aims for the more detailed reflection of the lyrics in the music than Orliński and Cencic do.

Perfecting his performing mastery, a vocalist can involve some subtle dynamic gradation in "Pena tiranna" aria because they serve as one of the means of musical development in this work. Against the backdrop of the sarabande repeating rhythm all the expressive performing nuances help to break its static character. Some rhythmic changes are possible if they can bring out the emotions of the aria better.

In the middle part a vocalist can find some contrasting means of expression that will serve a more prominent accentuation. It is also necessary to find such performing methods that will help develop a musical image. For that end, a vocalist may use more detailed agogic and dynamic shades and articulatory means: *legato*, *non legato*. The rhythmic pattern also can be varied (the notes may be prolonged or shortened). For instance, making an even rhythm sharper by dotting makes music more expressive. The inner contrast and

expressivity of the second part helps the aria to develop more intensively.

In 1773, Handel created another opera, “Orlando”, turning to the chivalric epic. In the aria «Sorge infausta una procella» Zoroastro tells his accompanying spirits to turn a grove into a dark cave where he tries to recapture Orlando’s sanity. The «Sorge infausta una procella» aria is a typical example of a bravura solo number representing a storm, both in nature and in the character’s emotions. These are the lyrics of the aria: “Let the ominous storm rise, / darkening sky and sea, – / The lucky star will shine after, / Brightening everyone’s heart up.”

According to baroque aesthetics, an aria bravura can have many ornaments, roulades, vocalizations, and a wide range melody. Exactly these means G. Handel is used in the «Sorge infausta una procella» aria. It has a three-part form da capo, and its reprise repeats the first part in full. The dramatic c-moll tonality defines this vocal number together with the fast tempo and the rush movement that begins already in a developed orchestra introduction. The aria theme of an instrumental constitution appears firstly in the orchestra, and then comes into the vocal part, thus creating a sort of competition between a voice and virtuoso passages of violins, which are typical for the baroque era. The theme is accompanied by figurations of sixteenth notes, which makes stronger the rapid character of the music.

The vocal part begins with fourth and fifth ascending leaps that cover an octave. The movement in the backward direction follows with eighth notes. Then active leaps for a fourth, an octave, a sixth appear in the melody. In the end of the first phrase the long vocalizations come. The vocalization on the word *ch’ognicor* lasts for six bars, composed of the running sixteenths and a thriller on a fourth note.

The second phrase begins with a melodic turn with an intonation of a diminished seventh. This striking dissonance in the beginning of the melody immediately creates tension. Then the composer introduces a diatonic sequence, a segment of which is a descending seventh. In the development of the sequence, it gives a major or a minor seventh alternately. Later a rhetorical figure of *zirculatio* appears in the vocal part: a melodic turn built on minor thirds repeats. The phrase endings have long vocalizations.

The closing melodic phrase of the first part is based on the descending conjunct movement for a decima, followed by a descending perfect fourth. In whole, the melodic line descends for almost two octaves, reaching G in the great octave. Such a rhetoric figure symbolizes going into an abyss. The last phrase of the part repeats the opening melodic turn, but downward.

The transition to the second part uses the same orchestra interlude as in the beginning of the aria. The key change to Es-dur in the second part makes a contrast. The vocal part is also based on a different theme. It consists of leaps on thirds, fifths, octaves. The phrase begins with winding melodic

movement and ends with a long descent. This is the principle of the whole part.

The aria «Sorge infausta una procella» is technically highly demanding. The bravura character of the melody comes from the number of difficult turns and passages interchanging in the fast tempo. There are broad leaps for octaves, seventh, phrases based on a winding melodic movement including different intervals. The scale-like passages are long, up to one and a half octaves. The usual repetitions and sequences come in to accentuate a specific turn or a striking leap of a melody. However, the most virtuoso part of the aria is the performing of the long vocalizations. The longest one in the word *ch’ognicor* lasts for six bars. It includes groups of the four sixteenths with two types of melodic movement: a conjunct movement for a third with a return to the first tone and an interchange between motions for a second or a third. The four sixteenth groups are linked through a descending third motion or an ascending second motion. The first variant is less comfortable for singing and demands a careful approach to the intonation. The fourth with thrillers come in leaps (for a third, a fourth) which is also difficult for a singer.

It is obvious that a vocalist has to take a breath before a change in the melodic movement. That is exactly what an Italian bass baritone Lorenzo Regazzo does in his virtuoso performer’s interpretation of the «Sorge infausta una procella» aria. He constructs this vocal number upon a powerful movement, constant drive forward. Only in the cadences of the main parts of the aria Lorenzo Regazzo slows the movement underlining the gravity of the spoken words. The singer uses the principle of “rhythmical dynamics” that states that a fast movement matches with a dynamic shade forte [3, p. 14].

This shows how the performing of baroque arias demands of a singer a good knowledge in the field of artistic implementation of the baroque composers’ musical texts. Our analysis of the «Pena tiranna» and «Sorge infausta una procella» arias by G. Handel shows that the composer used all the means of the musical language to create a specific type of an aria and a matching affect. The singer’s choice of the dynamics, tempo, and articulatory means is caused by the affect – these are a sorrowful lament aria and a bravura aria representing a storming nature. The analysis of the performer’s interpretations by Max Emanuel Cencic, Jakub Józef Orliński, Philippe Jaroussky, Cecilia Bartoli, Lorenzo Regazzo proves how these singers have a beautiful mastery of all vocal skills needed for the baroque repertoire and use elements of variation and improvisation.

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